

hwdbg: Debugging Hardware Like Software

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Abstract

Debugging hardware designs presents unique and significant challenges compared to software debugging. Software simulators often fail to uncover design issues arising from physical constraints or incorrect elaboration. Traditional hardware debugging tools typically lack flexibility, ease of use, and robust real-time interaction, slowing down the development and potentially compromising security.

We present HWDBG which eases hardware debugging by introducing software debugging concepts. Unlike existing approaches, HWDBG allows stepping through the hardware design cycle-by-cycle, visualizing waveforms, and inspecting values (e.g., like a logical analyzer). Users can script both passive and active debugging, modifying signals in real time. Furthermore, it has the potential for reverse engineering and chip fuzzing by injecting random signals to test functionality under different conditions. A key insight allowing HWDBG to achieve these goals is that, unlike existing approaches, it can be synthesized as an FPGA, directly interacting with the device under test in real time. We provide an open-source prototype.

CCS Concepts

- **Security and privacy** → **Hardware reverse engineering**; • **Hardware** → **Board- and system-level test**.

Keywords

Hardware Debugging, Hardware Testing, Fuzzing, Logic Analyzer

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1 Introduction

The design and deployment of hardware components play a key role in the rapid advancement of system development. As the complexity of systems increase, ensuring functionality, reliability, and security becomes more challenging. Traditional debugging methods struggle

to keep up with modern architectures and high-speed operations, necessitating a more efficient and versatile approach.

One major limitation of existing hardware debugging tools, such as the Xilinx Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA) [32], is their lack of flexibility and ease of use compared to software debugging environments, offering event-driven monitoring and scripting capabilities [13]. These tools provide limited real-time interaction, require cumbersome setup and significant manual intervention, making debugging time-consuming and error-prone. Additionally, they often lack essential features like signal manipulation or software-like scripting interfaces, further hindering the debugging process.

Conversely, hardware simulators like Questa [27] and Cadence's Incisive [3] offer powerful debugging and verification capabilities across different levels of abstraction, from RTL to gate-level simulations. However, they require extensive setup and are not well-suited for rapid prototyping or iterative design. While invaluable for early verification, simulators struggle to expose issues related to physical constraints or FPGA implementations, limiting their effectiveness in later stages of development.

Furthermore, the growing fields of reverse engineering and chip fuzzing introduce new opportunities and challenges for hardware debugging. Manipulating signals and exposing chips to diverse test scenarios are essential for identifying vulnerabilities, enhancing security, and ensuring hardware robustness.

These shortcomings highlight the need for a more adaptable, efficient, and user-friendly hardware debugging solution—one that bridges the gap between hardware and software debugging paradigms.

Research Objectives. We introduce HWDBG, an innovative hardware debugger design that redefines traditional hardware debugging methods by incorporating principles from software debugging, such as step-through execution, waveform visualization, and value inspection. HWDBG provides a powerful, intuitive tool for debugging fabricated chips and IP cores. It offers a unified platform to detect issues in hardware designs, including those brought by different cross-layer optimizations [12]. Beyond traditional debugging, HWDBG also empowers reverse engineering efforts by enabling precise signal tracing, real-time circuit manipulation, and automated analysis of proprietary hardware, making it an invaluable tool for security researchers and analysts.

The core concept behind HWDBG is enabling security researchers and hardware engineers to execute custom actions in the shortest relevant interval within a digital circuit: the rising and falling edges of the clock cycle. HWDBG stands out by integrating the strengths of

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both industrial and academic tools, offering a comprehensive solution that addresses the limitations of current hardware debugging practices. Unlike traditional tools that focus solely on simulation or require manual investigation, HWDBG provides a seamless debugging experience that mimics software debugging environments. It allows real-time interaction with hardware, including on-the-fly signal modification and detailed waveform analysis. This level of interaction is essential for debugging modern, increasingly complex hardware systems. By enabling step-through execution and value inspection at runtime, HWDBG offers a pioneering approach that enhances not only hardware debugging but also reverse engineering, allowing researchers to analyze, manipulate, and uncover the inner workings of complex digital systems.

Contributions. We offer the following key contributions:

- **Debugging Hardware Like Software:** We show that software debugging concepts can be applied to hardware debugging, providing a unified framework for debugging complex hardware systems, and enabling software-like scripting for both passive and active debugging strategies.
- **Robust Debugging Experience:** HWDBG provides capabilities not found in conventional debuggers or integrated logic analyzers, including on-the-fly signal modification and step-through debugging at the clock cycle level, allowing detailed introspection and manipulation of signals.
- **Reverse Engineering and Chip Fuzzing:** HWDBG enables advanced signal monitoring (passive) and manipulation (active), making it a promising tool for enhancing the effectiveness of reverse engineering and chip fuzzing techniques.
- **Open-source and Customizable Tool:** HWDBG is released as an open-source tool¹, offering accessibility and customization for users based on their specific needs.
- **Integration with FPGAs:** HWDBG can be synthesized into FPGAs, enabling debugging of high-frequency signals and offering a practical solution for real-world testing conditions.

2 Background

Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). FPGAs are integrated circuits that can be configured after manufacturing. Their reprogrammability enables diverse applications for electronic design and testing. This flexibility also makes FPGAs ideal for developing and deploying hardware debugging tools like HWDBG.

Programmable Logic (PL) and Processing System (PS). FPGAs consist of the PL and PS components, which work together for a flexible platform. The PL (FPGA part) includes configurable logic blocks and resources for implementing custom circuits, enabling hardware accelerators and processing pipelines. The PS (processor) is a pre-designed element, such as an ARM processor, with memory controllers and interfaces, supporting general-purpose computing (e.g., Linux). The integration of PL and PS in a single device creates systems that combine hardware and software processing.

Block RAM (BRAM). Block RAM (BRAM) provides high-speed on-chip memory in FPGAs. BRAMs consist of configurable SRAM blocks, allowing flexible instantiation and interconnection to meet

design requirements. BRAM offers lower latency, higher bandwidth, and reduced power consumption compared to external memory.

3 Related Work

Hardware debugging has advanced significantly, driven by the need for more efficient and reliable tools. Various methodologies and tools address challenges like side-channel attacks, synchronization issues, and verification. This section overviews key developments in hardware debugging and their relevance to HWDBG.

Side-Channel Attack Mitigation. Side-channel attacks pose a significant threat to hardware security, exploiting physical caveats such as power consumption, electromagnetic emissions, and timing information to extract sensitive data. There have been studies to develop theoretically-backed hardware-level mitigation for each of these side channels. For instance, hardware masking [10] is known to mitigate the majority of power-based side-channel attacks. Moreover, different attack-specific detection and mitigation mechanisms are developed. For instance, advanced physical side-channels such as optical probing [17], static-power attack [5], and impedance side-channels [21] can be detected and mitigated via high resolution delay-based sensors [25], and hardware reconfiguration [19]. Tools like *ChipWhisperer* [22] and Riscure's *Inspector* [24] have been developed to facilitate side-channel analysis and testing. *ChipWhisperer*, for instance, integrates hardware and software to perform side-channel attacks and analyze vulnerabilities in cryptographic implementations. The HWDBG debugger builds on these concepts by incorporating robust mechanisms to monitor hardware using different sensors, ensuring enhanced security in hardware designs.

Communication and Signal Interception. Synchronization between hardware debugger components is essential for accurate data capture and analysis. The OpenCores project [23] offers open-source hardware modules, including synchronization modules that ensure seamless data flow. Likewise, HWDBG uses an advanced synchronization module to coordinate data transfers, preventing loss and preserving debugging integrity.

Efficient signal interception is crucial for real-time hardware debugging. Tools like Xilinx's Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA) [32] and Intel's SignalTap [11] enable in-depth signal analysis and data processing, helping developers monitor and interpret FPGAs signal activity. HWDBG enhances this by integrating an advanced interpreter module that processes signals, determines actions, and generates responses, streamlining the debugging workflow.

Hardware Monitoring and Logic Analyzers. Effective hardware debugging relies on tools and IP cores that enable real-time signal monitoring and modification. One notable example is *PHMon* (Programmable Hardware Monitor) [6], which provides a flexible, programmable platform for tracking hardware events in real-time. By integrating hardware and software, PHMon allows developers to observe and manipulate signals without halting the system. Additionally, researchers have explored adapting software techniques like fuzzing [28] for hardware testing, demonstrating that software-based approaches can effectively enhance hardware debugging.

Xilinx's Vivado Debug IP and Intel's FPGA Debug and Monitoring IP Cores offer comprehensive solutions for real-time hardware monitoring and control. These IP cores integrate seamlessly into

¹Our code is available at <https://url.hyperdbg.org/hwdbg-repo/>.

Figure 1: High-level overview of hwdbg’s sub-systems and signal flows.

FPGA designs, providing capabilities for capturing and analyzing signal activities. Furthermore, ARM’s CoreSight technology [1] provides extensive debugging and trace capabilities for ARM-based systems. CoreSight includes components like the Embedded Trace Macrocell (ETM) and the Instrumentation Trace Macrocell (ITM), which support detailed tracing of program execution and data flow. These components enable developers to monitor and modify signals at the clock cycle granular level, aiding in the identification of bugs and performance bottlenecks. hwdbg offers comprehensive state-of-the-art hardware monitoring and logic analysis capabilities, as well as unique features such as incorporating sensors, to offer a robust and reliable platform for hardware debugging.

4 Overview

hwdbg is a comprehensive hardware debugging framework designed to facilitate testing, analysis, and fault diagnosis in digital systems. hwdbg integrates multiple subsystems, including fuzzing and testing, debugging capabilities, debugging sensors, and communication modules. They enable advanced functionalities such as fault injection, signal inspection, and breakpoint emulation, providing a flexible and modular approach to debugging.

Figure 1 shows hwdbg’s primary subsystems and signal flows. hwdbg runs on the PL of an FPGA. It interfaces with the user through the PS, offering software-like hardware debugging. It connects directly to the DUT through input/output pins. The Debugging modules support signal inspection, logic analysis, and breakpoint emulation for real-time hardware testing. They also include tools for automated fuzzing, fault injection, and signal manipulation, to evaluate DUT functionalities. Debugging Sensors, such as ring oscillators, voltage sensors, and temperature sensors, provide critical data about hardware behavior. Finally, the Communication modules handle signal transmission, interpretation, and synchronization, ensuring efficient coordination between subsystems.

hwdbg makes hardware debugging more like software debugging. For example, stepping through instructions is common in

software debugging. Although hardware lacks a direct equivalent to instructions, hwdbg provides similar functionality by controlling the clock signal.

Our design can be synthesized into FPGAs, allowing hwdbg to run directly on hardware for real-time debugging and testing, which is important for testing high-frequency signals (at the speed range of FPGAs) and for scenarios where a simulation does not capture the full spectrum of potential hardware behaviors. Moreover, our approach supports debugging chips in a black-box setting, assuming that the chip’s source code is not available. hwdbg can receive inputs through multiple means, including direct user input via command-line interfaces, script files containing test cases or debugging instructions.

During the design process, we addressed scalability and performance by adopting a modular architecture. It allows for seamless scaling by adding or removing components as needed. To maintain data consistency across PS/PL and external debuggers, we used advanced synchronization mechanisms and error-checking protocols. We also chose a microservices architecture over a monolithic approach for its potential scalability and maintainability benefits.

5 Debugging Sensors

Sensors play a vital role in hardware debugging by providing real-time system and environmental data. They aid in fault identification, performance optimization, side-channel analysis, and reliability assurance. While similar sensors have been already used for offensive remote side-channel attacks on FPGA [33] as well as protective defensive methods [20], to the best of authors’ knowledge, hwdbg is the first work to offer said sensors as primitives in a debugging and testing tool, which in conjunction with comprehensive scripting capabilities, can greatly extend the flexibility and efficiency of black/gray-box hardware debugging and fuzzing, while maintaining physically accurate and high-fidelity readings.

This section explores the use of sensors in side-channel analysis and their integration into hwdbg.

Side-channels. Hardware side-channel attacks exploit microchip and IP core characteristics to extract sensitive information without using primary data channels. Sensors provide data based on attributes like power consumption, electromagnetic emissions, temperature, and timing, which correlate with specific operations or data being processed. For example, voltage and power sensors track power fluctuations, enabling Differential Power Analysis (DPA) to reveal cryptographic keys [16]. Temperature sensors detect thermal changes, facilitating thermal imaging attacks [14]. Time-to-digital converters (TDCs) and frequency sensors capture high-resolution timing data, enabling timing analysis attacks [26]. Ring oscillators (RO) identify signal delay variations for delay-based attacks [9]. On the other hand, similar sensors can also be used for defensive purposes. For instance, clock sensors detect anomalies caused by tampering or glitching [8]. Furthermore, delay-based sensors might be used to detect laser-based probing side-channel attacks [20].

By capturing and analyzing unintended post-silicon emissions or leakages, hardware engineers and security researchers can reason about hardware side channels.

Sensors in HWDBG. To aid analysis of microchips and IP cores, HWDBG implements the following sensors:

- A **ring oscillator (RO)** is an electronic oscillator with an odd number of inverters connected in a loop, generating a periodic signal through continuous state switching. Its frequency is influenced by voltage, temperature, and manufacturing variations, making it useful for detecting parameter changes.
- A **Time-to-Digital Converter (TDC)** measures time intervals with high precision by converting event time differences into digital values, providing accurate event timing.
- **Input Delay Element (IDELAYE3)** is a programmable delay line used for signal timing and synchronization in digital circuits, allowing precise delay adjustments to align signals with clock timing. Security researchers may exploit IDELAYE3 to introduce deliberate signal delays [20], affecting power consumption, electromagnetic emissions, or timing, which can lead to side-channel leaks. IDELAYE3 is integrated into HWDBG to aid side-channel analysis.
- **Voltage sensors** track voltage levels in hardware systems, ensuring optimal operation and preventing damage from overvoltage or undervoltage.
- **Frequency sensors** measure the operating frequency of hardware components to ensure they function within specified parameters.
- **Temperature sensors** monitor the thermal state of hardware components and ensure thermal stability [29]. In HWDBG, they help detect hotspots and enable dynamic thermal management strategies to possibly leak data from the debuggee.
- **Clock sensors** monitor and verify clock signals, ensuring that clock signals stay within specified tolerances for timing and synchronization [7]. Using techniques like phase-locked loops (PLLs) and clock distribution networks, they detect discrepancies and maintain system synchronization.

6 Communication

HWDBG has four main communication modules that ensure effective communication between PL and PS and prevent conflicts that

could lead to corruption or invalid data. Our communication protocol follows a packet-based design between sender and receiver. These packets contain special mandatory headers to check for the integrity of the packet and prevent communication errors as well as specifying which component in the debugger/debuggee is responsible for handling the receiving packet and the corresponding action. To achieve this, we designed a custom communication protocol, enabling data exchange through shared memory. Communication between PL and PS is facilitated by a shared BlockRAM (BRAM) module. Since only one port is shared between PS and PL, and the BlockRAM has a single port, simultaneous read/write operations are not possible. These modules manage data flow to prevent conflicts that could lead to corruption or invalid data. Once valid data is received, the Interpreting Module processes the packet and may send data based on its interpretation.

Sending Module. transmits data from PL (HWDBG) to PS. It encapsulates the outgoing data into appropriate-sized packets, adds data headers, manages necessary handshaking protocols, and adjust data fields as required to ensure sound transmission of data.

Receiving Module. captures incoming data from PS and passes it to the HWDBG for further processing. It monitors the designated PS to PL port for incoming data packets, retrieves them, checks for validity, and forwards them to the appropriate components within the debugger for interpretation or storage.

Synchronization Module. plays a crucial role in preventing data corruption and ensuring the integrity of communication between the debugger and the PL/PS by arbitrating the timing of communications. Additionally, our Xilinx-FPGA-compatible specification of BRAM exposes distinct ports to PL and PS, thus mitigating the issue of simultaneous access to a shared port by design.

Interpretation Module. decodes the successfully received data from PS, interprets its meaning or purpose, and triggers the necessary actions/responses within HWDBG. This module is responsible for parsing incoming commands, executing debugging operations, or generating responses to be sent back to the PS.

BlockRAM (BRAM) Simulator. BlockRAM is one of the key components that facilitates several functionalities of HWDBG, including the communication between PL and PS, as well as other capabilities (e.g. Logic Analyzer). Given the lack of support of Chisel language [2] for BlockRAM components, HWDBG utilizes its custom-developed BlockRAM simulator module, featuring input/output ports compatible with Xilinx FPGA BlockRAMs, ensuring cross-compatibility and accurate simulation. Although fully customizable, we found 8 KB flip-flop modules to be reasonable for most functionalities of HWDBG. Specifically, by default, we allocate 4 KB directionally-dedicated memory regions to establish a full-duplex communication channel between PL and PS. We perform extensive delay-characteristics-aware testing of the BRAM module by transferring data between PL and PS modules and interpreting and validating the integrity of the data based on the underlying communication protocol. The simulation was executed using cocotb [4], with Verilator [31] and Icarus [30] serving as the backend tools.

7 Applications

This section discusses several debugging modules supported by HWDBG and establishes parallels to already existing tools. We consider both traditional debugging and applications in system security.

7.1 Debugging

For a tool to qualify as a debugger, it must provide several essential functionalities. These include fine-grained and coarse-grained monitoring and control over both the execution and data of the debuggee program. In software debugging, this entails reading and writing register- and memory-level data, stepping through individual instructions, and setting conditional or unconditional breakpoints. We draw a parallel between these software debugging features and those offered by HWDBG (in that order):

- **Signal Inspection and Modification:** HWDBG enables fine-grained monitoring and modification of individual signals exposed to the debugger at the finest temporal resolution of the debuggee hardware (clock signal). HWDBG supports automated signal monitoring and manipulation through by allowing execution of user-defined custom scripts
- **Logic Analyzer:** By combining the fine-grained ability of HWDBG to read and write signals at high resolution with the customizable BlockRAM modules, HWDBG can store signal values at various user-defined timing stages. These logs can then be forwarded to the PS for visualization and analysis, effectively enabling HWDBG to function as a logic analyzer.
- **Instruction Stepping Emulation:** HWDBG is capable of treating the clock signal in a special manner that provides control over the execution of the circuit, globally lockstepped to the user-controlled clock signal. Accompanied by the capability to pause operation, thorough read/write capability to signals and BRAMs, and advancing the execution of the debuggee with manually provided or programmed/scripted clock edges, it offers a debugging primitive similar to instructions step-in of software debuggers for hardware modules. However, this feature is not applicable to circuits with internally provided (non-exposed) clock signals.
- **Breakpoint Emulation:** HWDBG enables real-time evaluation of user-defined conditions on signals during computation. It can pause execution and trigger custom scripts to perform specified actions, such as halting or applying user-defined inputs. This serves as the hardware equivalent of software conditional and unconditional breakpoints.

7.2 Reverse Engineering

Researchers have explored FPGA IP reverse engineering [15] using various methodologies. Most of these methodologies involve extracting data from the IP and performing offline statistical and satisfiability testing [15]. The HWDBG infrastructure allows researchers to deploy the reverse engineering engines directly within the FPGA fabric by embedding the analysis scripts as a debugging function. This can significantly increase performance of the process, as both data transfer and analysis occur locally on the FPGA's fabric.

7.3 Fuzzing and Reliability Testing

HWDBG is designed to offer extensive fuzzing and testing capabilities to identify potential vulnerabilities and unexpected behaviors. Since HWDBG is intended to support black-box modules (without access to RTL source code), the white-box-specific definitions of anomalies [28] do not cover the full scope of testing considered in HWDBG. Therefore, we regard anomalies as any unintended state that occurs in the debuggee module, and we explore the following two approaches for discovering such unanticipated behaviors:

- **Oracle-based Testing** assumes knowledge of the expected output of the debuggee for a given set of testing/fuzzing inputs. In such case, HWDBG can automatically apply inputs to the debuggee and check for discrepancies with the oracle.
- **Oracle-less Testing** considers the lack of an oracle model for the debuggee. HWDBG offers a wide range of sensors (Section 5) that can be placed in user-defined positions to expose various electrical and physical properties of the underlying circuit, allowing for the discovery of an unexpected state in the underlying hardware with outlier sensor readings.

HWDBG supports several mechanisms to purposefully manipulate the inputs to the debuggee to examine the robustness and reliability of the underlying hardware, such as:

- **Automated Fuzzing** is the automatic generation and injection of large volumes of random or semi-random inputs into a system to trigger corner cases or faults. HWDBG's fuzzing module can be used to enhance the reliability and security of black-box chips by finding issues before mass production.
- **Fault Injection** includes the use of fault injection methods (e.g. physical, logical, and software-based) to test the robustness of hardware modules. HWDBG can incorporate this to simulate a wide range of real-world fault scenarios and ensure graceful recovery of the system.
- **Cutting the Signal** involves intentionally breaking the continuity of a signal path (e.g., the clock signal) to simulate open-circuit faults or to test the system's response to sudden loss of input. HWDBG can use this to test the robustness of communication links and critical signal paths.
- **Changing Clock Domain Using PWM** entails varying the duty cycle of the clock signal supplied to a part of the circuit. It can be used to test the behavior of the hardware under different clock conditions (e.g., overclocking, underclocking, and clock glitches) to identify timing-related vulnerabilities.

8 Evaluation

This section analyzes the impact of the proposed hardware debugger and compares its evaluation results with similar tools (Xilinx ILA).

The HWDBG testing artifacts primarily target AMD Xilinx FPGAs, with experiments conducted on a ZCU104 development board. This board features a Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC chip, which includes a quad-core ARM Cortex-A53 application processor and a dual-core Cortex-R5 real-time processor. The Programmable Logic (PL) and Processing Subsystem (PS) communicate through various shared channels and interfaces using the AXI-Stream protocol, enabling the debugging process. FPGA synthesis and implementation are performed using AMD Xilinx Vivado 2023.2, while the application development relies on Vitis IDE 2023.2. The debugger's core

is developed in Scala with the Chisel language [2] and leverages FIRRTL [18] (CIRCT) for automated Verilog transformation.

8.1 The Impact of Proposed Hardware

The introduction of HWDBG significantly enhances FPGA debugging and testing by detecting functional anomalies, monitoring signals, and utilizing sensor data to uncover rare issues. This may improve hardware reliability, reducing the risk of field failures. Additionally, HWDBG has the potential of strengthening security by identifying vulnerabilities through automated fuzzing and fault injection, mitigating risks like side-channel attacks.

8.2 Comparison with Xilinx ILA

This section compares HWDBG’s debugging capabilities with the industry-standard Xilinx ILA, used as a baseline.

8.2.1 Scripting Comparison. The scripting capabilities of Xilinx ILA and HWDBG highlight significant differences in how they define and manage trigger conditions in the debugging process.

Xilinx ILA utilizes a state-machine-based approach, allowing users to define sequences of conditions and actions that determine when a trigger occurs. This method provides structured control over debugging events by leveraging signal values and counters to determine transitions between states.

In contrast, HWDBG adopts a procedural scripting style, resembling traditional programming paradigms. Instead of defining state transitions, users directly manipulate variables and apply conditional logic to determine trigger events. This approach is more aligned with software development practices, making it easier for programmers to adapt to hardware debugging. With a structure that emphasizes step-by-step execution and explicit condition handling, HWDBG provides a flexible alternative for those who prefer a more familiar, software-like scripting experience.

8.2.2 In-depth Feature Comparison. As presented in Table 1, while Xilinx ILA outperforms HWDBG in speed, offering faster data capture and processing, HWDBG provides a broader range of intuitive and powerful debugging and testing features. These features enhance the process of identifying vulnerabilities in hardware modules, capabilities that Xilinx ILA lacks. Although both Xilinx ILA and HWDBG support event-triggering mechanisms, such as **breakpoints** based on specific conditions, HWDBG offers an extensive selection of **debugging sensors**. These sensors provide deeper insights into system performance and can detect anomalies that may not be apparent through signal monitoring alone. HWDBG enables **on-the-fly signal modifications**, allowing dynamic adjustments and testing without FPGA reconfiguration, making debugging more flexible and responsive than ILA. It can interpret **complex computations** for deeper analysis and supports **software-style stepping** and **fault injection** to enhance design robustness. Inspired by software programming, HWDBG uses a **simpler scripting language** for an intuitive scripting experience. Additionally, it can actively produce **fuzzing signals**, a capability unavailable in Xilinx ILA.

9 Limitations

High-Frequency Debugging. HWDBG is unsuitable for capturing and analyzing signals from high-frequency chips (e.g., 4 GHz CPUs).

Table 1: Comparison of HWDBG and Xilinx ILA.

Feature	HWDBG (dslang)	Xilinx ILA (TSM)
Can act as a logic analyzer	✓	✓
Speed comparison	Slower	Faster
Can trigger an event (e.g., a breakpoint)	✓	✓
Has debugging sensors	✓	✗
Can modify signals on the fly (configurable)	✓	✗
Can interpret complex computations	✓	✗
Supports on-the-fly configuration	✓	✗
Notify the debugger without triggering event	✓	✗
Supports software stepping	✓	✗
Simplicity of state machine scripting	Simple scripting	More complex
Stepping fault-injection/signal manipulation	✓	✗
Active debugging (producing fuzzing signals)	✓	✗

Frequency Bottleneck. Certain scripting primitives in HWDBG may reduce the FPGA’s operational clock, limiting the debuggee module’s execution frequency (IP core).

BlockRAM Capacity. HWDBG’s logic analyzer and fuzzing rely on BRAM, which fills rapidly (e.g., 11 Mbit on a ZCU104 board in under a second). Users must selectively capture traces.

10 Conclusion

We presented HWDBG, a novel hardware debugging and testing tool that incorporates primitives from software debugging and hardware security fields to offer a unified framework that enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of hardware vulnerability discovery. We illustrated how software debugging concepts can be applied to hardware debugging to create intuitive debugging primitives for analysis of both white-box and black-box IP cores. Furthermore, we showcased a range of security-oriented features embedded in the design of HWDBG, including signal manipulation, fault injection, chip fuzzing, and an extensive array of hardware sensors, commonly used in the field of hardware security. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, this is the first work to propose the utilization of such sensors outside the domain of side-channel literature and in a hardware debugging and testing context. We discussed how these primitives can be leveraged in a manual, semi-manual, or automated manner to facilitate the discovery of potential vulnerabilities. Our prototype implementation of HWDBG is open-source and highly customizable to meet the specific needs of different users. Furthermore, our prototype is fully synthesizable into Xilinx FPGAs, which provides hardware engineers with a practical solution for debugging high-frequency signals and modern hardware designs and opens up new possibilities for real-time debugging and IP core testing. With the growing complexity of electronic systems, we hope that HWDBG stands as a useful tool to address the challenges and opportunities of the hardware development landscape and enable researchers and engineers to enhance the robustness and security of hardware systems.

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